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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
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- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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THE STRUCTURAL MODEL OF STUDENTS' ENGAGEMENT IN LIFELONG LEARNING

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Abstract: This article analyzes the structural model of students' engagement in lifelong learning, highlighting the socio-psychological characteristics related to students' commitment to continuous education. The study also reviews current models of educational engagement proposed by both local and international researchers. Students' engagement in lifelong learning is considered an independent socio-psychological phenomenon that emerges from the interaction between students and their social environment, including educational institutions, study groups, professional representatives, teachers, and others.

Key words: structural model of engagement, engagement in lifelong learning, structure of engagement in lifelong learning, four- and five-component models of engagement, professional environment.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada talabalarning umrbod ta'limga jalb etilishining (engagement) strukturaviy modeli tahlil qilinib, ularning uzluksiz ta'limga sodiqligi bilan bog'liq ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlar yoritiladi. Shuningdek, mahalliy va xorijiy tadqiqotchilar tomonidan taklif qilingan ta'limga jalb etilishning mavjud modellari ham ko'rib chiqiladi. Talabalarning umrbod ta'limga jalb etilishi ta'lim muassasalari, o'quv guruhlari, kasbiy vakillar, o'qituvchilar va boshqa ijtimoiy muhit subyektlari bilan o'zaro ta'sir natijasida shakllanadigan mustaqil ijtimoiy-psixologik hodisa sifatida qaraladi.

Kalit so'zlar: jalb etilishning strukturaviy modeli, umrbod ta'limga jalb etilish, umrbod ta'limda jalb etilishning tuzilishi, to'rt va besh komponentli jalb etilish modellari, kasbiy muhit.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется структурная модель вовлечённости студентов в непрерывное образование, раскрываются социально-психологические характеристики, связанные с их приверженностью к обучению на протяжении всей жизни. Кроме того, рассматриваются современные модели вовлечённости в образование, предложенные отечественными и зарубежными исследователями. Вовлечённость студентов в непрерывное образование рассматривается как самостоятельное социально-психологическое явление, формирующееся во взаимодействии студентов с их социальным окружением, включая образовательные учреждения, учебные группы, профессиональных представителей, преподавателей и других участников.

Ключевые слова: структурная модель вовлечённости, вовлечённость в непрерывное образование, структура вовлечённости в непрерывное образование, четырёх- и пятикомпонентные модели вовлечённости, профессиональная среда.

INTRODUCTION

Students' engagement in lifelong learning reflects the level of effort and energy they invest in performing educational activities, as well as the emotional experiences, cognitive, motivational, and meaningful processes associated with learning. Managing students' engagement in lifelong learning ensures the achievement of the ultimate goals of educational programs. A high level of engagement supports students in actively acquiring new knowledge and developing their professional competencies throughout the educational process.

When analyzing scholarly work on the issue of engagement, it is important to note that many researchers have attempted to conceptualize engagement as a multidimensional construct that includes several components. It should also be noted that within the field of organizational psychology, numerous studies have been conducted on the structure of engagement, with a primary focus on work-related activity and the organizational context.

Some researchers, when studying engagement, consider behavior as the sole and dominant criterion, evaluating behavioral manifestations of involvement as objective indicators. However, it should be emphasized that even when an individual demonstrates external activity and participation, this may not always be supported by internal cognitive and emotional engagement. In other words, we believe that in the study of engagement,

not only behavioral aspects but also other dimensions should be taken into account. When examining the model of students' engagement in lifelong learning, attention can be given to certain structural models that have been considered in various contexts—not only within educational activities but also in the context of work.

LITERATURE REVIEW

J. Fredricks' three-factor model includes three components: behavioral, emotional, and cognitive. Behavioral engagement is reflected in students' verbal and non-verbal actions. Emotional engagement relates to students' sense of belonging to the school (e.g., their relationships with peers, teachers, and other adults). Cognitive engagement is manifested in a sense of personal responsibility during the learning process and in reflective thinking while solving complex problems. Each of these three components is considered essential for understanding students' engagement. The author also notes that many studies tend to focus primarily on one aspect of student engagement—mainly the behavioral component[6].

The four-factor model of engagement includes academic, behavioral, cognitive, and psychological components[8]. Academic engagement variables include the amount of time spent on tasks, grades earned by the end of the course, and the completion of homework assignments. Behavioral engagement variables include class attendance, disciplinary actions taken against the student, and voluntary participation in classroom and extracurricular activities. Cognitive and psychological components reflect cognitive and motivational factors. These four components are not necessarily required for students to be consistently engaged. Rather, they are used to understand the various characteristics that influence the relationship between students and their learning environment[7].

In another model, students' engagement is characterized by energy, dedication, and absorption. N.A. Fedorova (2011), when describing the structure of student engagement, identified two main components: cognitive component, characterized by the assimilation of learning material, motivational component, which reflects interest in acquiring professional knowledge and developing professional skills. In the context of organizational psychology, K. Maslach, W. Schaufeli, and other scholars identified the following components of engagement: vigor, dedication to work, and self-efficacy.

J. Meyer and N. Allen, along with P. Morrow, considered engagement as an emotional component of commitment. Researchers from the CIPD (Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development) in the United Kingdom define the key components of engagement as: Focus on the task, Satisfaction with one's role, and Loyalty to the organization, its goals, and values[7]. Based on the studies described above, it is important to note that a model of engagement in lifelong learning can be developed. Engagement in lifelong learning emerges in the process of an individual's professional development, and it reflects the learner's goal-directed activity in acquiring knowledge throughout their professional life. An analysis of the available literature on this issue suggests that in the structure of engagement in lifelong learning, both objective and subjective components can be distinguished.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The objective component is manifested at the behavioral level through external expressions (which are easily observable), and many engagement studies focus specifically on this level. The subjective component, on the other hand, is identified through internal processes of the individual and is not readily observable. These include beliefs, attitudes, needs, motivations, meanings, and so on. The study of subjective components is not as widespread. It is also important to highlight the interrelation between the objective and subjective components of engagement in lifelong learning. Furthermore, based on a deep and comprehensive study of the phenomenon of engagement in lifelong learning—as an integral part of professional development activities—Russian scholars, particularly N.V. Kiseleva (Doctor of Sciences, Moscow State University of Psychology and Education), have developed a five-component structural model of student engagement in lifelong learning.

In this model:

-The objective component is represented by the behavioral component.

-The subjective component is represented by four components: cognitive, emotional, motivational, and value-based.

In particular:

1.Cognitive Component (Reflects various perceptions of lifelong learning)

– Perceptions of lifelong learning, its level of necessity for professional development, and its importance within reference groups;

– Understanding of the learning environment (peer groups, teaching staff, and other groups involved in the educational process);

- Perceptions of one's professional future, self-efficacy, the ability to acquire professional knowledge and develop competencies, and the opportunity to realize creative potential within the profession;
- Perceptions of the “rational benefits” of lifelong learning — i.e., the ratio between the costs of education and the potential benefits (e.g., status, salary);
- Perceptions of the availability and quality of education;
- Confidence in one's professional future and the belief that investments made in education will lead to professional fulfillment and the achievement of desired outcomes.

2. Emotional Component(Reflects the affective attitude toward lifelong learning and the dominant emotions experienced during the educational process)

- Positive and negative emotions experienced during the learning and professional development process;
- Emotional evaluation of the learning process, its outcomes, and the content and format of educational programs;

- Degree of satisfaction with the learning process;
- Experiences of immersion or absorption during educational activities;
- Attitude toward the chosen profession and its perceived attractiveness.

3. Behavioral Component(Reflects the individual's behavioral activity in the learning process)

- Participation in lifelong learning programs and related activities;
- Completion of required formal educational procedures;
- Time allocated to learning;
- Level of activity and willingness to maintain or increase engagement in the future, including readiness to exert additional effort;

- Tendency to reduce effort in learning activities;
- Social interactions and engagement with other participants in the learning process, including gradual entry and integration into the professional environment.

4. Motivational Component(Reflects the perceived necessity of lifelong learning)

- The content and strength of the motivations underlying the student's educational activity (e.g., intrinsic vs. extrinsic motivation);
- The learner's professional needs that they plan to fulfill through education, including aspirations toward professional competence and achievement;
- Motivations related to personal growth and self-actualization that are satisfied in the course of learning.

5. Value-Based Component(Reflects the personal significance of lifelong learning and the values attributed to it by the individual)

- The importance of lifelong learning for professional activity;
- The personal value placed on one's profession, the aspiration to “be the best” in one's field, the importance of remaining competitive and in demand in the labor market;
- The significance of belonging to a professional group;
- The value of the professional environment itself;
- The presence of personal meaning in the educational process;
- The value of lifelong learning for personal and professional growth, as well as for self-realization;
- The voluntary nature of career choice, confidence in that choice, and the development of professional identity;
- The importance of lifelong learning for successful adaptation and socialization in modern conditions.

Analysis and Results

Based on various **combinations of behavioral and value-based components, as well as the degree to which these are expressed, N. Kiseleva identified four types of engagement:

1.Active Engagement(AE) Characterized by a high level of behavioral engagement combined with a strong value placed on education. The student actively participates in learning and attributes significant importance to the educational process.

2.Compelled Pseudo-Engagement(CPE) Characterized by high behavioral engagement, but low personal meaning and value attributed to the learning process and professional development. The student appears engaged, but this behavior is not supported by intrinsic motivation or perceived value.

3.Passive Engagement(PE) Characterized by low behavioral activity, yet accompanied by a high value placed on education. The student considers learning important but demonstrates minimal involvement in the educational process.

4. Lack of Engagement(LE) Characterized by both low behavioral engagement and low attribution of value to education. The student neither participates actively in learning nor considers it personally meaningful.

Engagement in lifelong learning can be regarded as a phenomenon arising during a person's professional development process. Engagement in the educational process reflects the learner's purposeful activity aimed

at a specific goal and includes the subjective evaluation of the importance of the learning process. It should also be noted that learners' engagement in the educational process has an uneven character. Specifically, during certain periods of learning activity, learners' involvement in the educational process may be high, while during other periods it may be lower. This phenomenon may be related to factors such as:

- crises in professional identity awareness;
- understanding the value of the competencies being acquired for future professional work;
- the level of satisfaction with the educational process; and so forth.

The dynamics of learners' engagement in lifelong learning are considered within the context of their interaction with the external environment and deserve special attention. When studying learner engagement as a socio-psychological phenomenon, it is necessary to examine it within the framework of the interaction between the individual and their environment: engagement is shaped by the influence of internal personal factors and external environmental factors (such as engagement with the professional environment, social groups, professional communities, and higher education institutions). These factors include:

- individual psychological and personal characteristics;
- the perception of one's own effectiveness and ability;
- the sense of success or failure;
- motivational characteristics and volitional qualities;
- the learner's engagement with professional communities, their interaction with higher education institutions, and other processes occurring in society and the immediate social environment.

Today, engagement in lifelong learning has become an integral part of the life of a modern specialist with a profession, where educational activity remains relevant throughout life. Engagement in lifelong learning facilitates the successful acquisition of new knowledge, skills, and competencies, which in turn helps better adapt to constantly changing conditions and enables the mastery of professional competencies necessary to remain competitive in the labor market.

UNESCO's "Education Strategy for 2014–2021" identifies lifelong learning as a "fundamental organizing principle" for all forms of education. This principle is based on the belief that the education system must support lifelong learning and create opportunities for formal, non-formal, and informal learning for people of all ages. In this process, the focus should not only be on providing knowledge and developing specific skills but also on cultivating broad competencies that serve to realize learners' potential. I.P. Pecheransky emphasizes that "one of the mega-trends of the new century, alongside demographic changes and globalization, is lifelong learning"[7]. Taking these characteristics into account when studying engagement in lifelong learning, three main areas of focus can be distinguished:

- Engagement in the educational process.
- Engagement in the development of professional competencies within the lifelong educational activity process.
- Engagement in social interactions with the professional environment, including teachers, other learners, and representatives of the chosen profession — owners of professional culture and competencies.

Each of these directions can be an independent object of research. For example, engagement in the educational process can be studied within pedagogy, even outside the context of lifelong learning. Engagement in professional development may be investigated in andragogy and acmeology. Engagement with the professional environment could be a topic of interest in organizational and social psychology. At the same time, in real-life conditions, all these phenomena are interrelated.

Thus, engagement in lifelong learning can be described as a multi-level system: sectors represent components of engagement, while levels reflect its substructures (subcomponents). Summarizing the existing materials, it is important to emphasize that "engagement in professional development" is the individual's striving to develop their professional competencies, the desire to accumulate life experience; consciously seeking opportunities for professional development within the social environment; manifested through the person's activity — that is, understanding their intentions, organizing professional development, and recognizing their responsibility towards this process.

"Engagement with the Professional Environment and Social Interaction".

Traditionally, the professional environment often defines the content of vocational education. Currently, numerous efforts are underway to adapt the educational process to the demands of the professional environment. However, this process is primarily implemented in higher education institutions and is not yet fully applied across all stages of the lifelong learning system. Throughout the educational activity, a gradual adaptation to the professional environment occurs. Over time, as learners engage in educational activities and develop professional competencies, the scope of their professional community expands, leading to a deeper understanding of professional norms and values, and the fulfillment of professional needs within significant social groups (reference groups).

This article seeks to further explore the essence of engagement with the professional environment from a social-psychological perspective. "Engagement with the professional environment" refers to an individual's active interaction with the professional milieu, manifested through behavioral activity both within and outside the environment, representing themselves as a member of that professional community. Such engagement is expressed through the individual's emotional attachment to the environment and their loyalty to the professional goals and values.

The professional environment, in turn, is a complex system comprising professional activity subjects, the conditions under which this activity takes place, and their interactions and mutual influences. It facilitates an individual's awareness of their professional affiliation, acceptance of professional principles, integration into professional culture, and ensures professional growth and development. Participants in the professional environment include competent specialists, newcomers (students and young professionals), professional groups and communities, higher education institutions, departments, organizations, and others.

Given the dynamic nature of engagement with the professional environment, the following stages are proposed:

1. Initial Stage. Engagement begins to form. The individual undergoes the process of career choice, finding the profession attractive. The intention to become a representative of the profession and to join the professional environment emerges. In some cases, career choice is influenced by familiarity with the professional environment and the appeal of its members. At this stage, the individual is not yet considered part of the professional environment.

2. Learning Professional Competencies and Initial Development, Orientation in the Professional Environment. This stage typically corresponds to the beginning of professional education, familiarization with professional language, norms, and rules, adaptation to labor requirements and conditions, and assimilation of accumulated educational experience. The individual acquires fundamental professional competencies and assumes a new social role (e.g., student in a particular profession). This stage concludes with psychological preparation and the formation of a desire to engage in the chosen professional activity.

3. Joining the Professional Environment and Adapting to Professional Activity. At this stage, the individual begins to perceive themselves as part of the professional environment, shares the community's values and traditions, and demonstrates behavior aligned with environmental demands. Professional identity is formed, conceptions of professional career become clearer, and core and specialized competencies develop. This stage concludes with adaptation to professional activity and self-recognition as a member of a specific profession.

4. "Deep Immersion in the Professional Environment."

During this stage, the individual's understanding of professional activity deepens, skills improve, and a sense of professional success emerges. The individual forms a professional stance and gains awareness of their own professional capabilities and limitations. An experience of interaction with the external environment as a representative of the professional community develops (and their professional status is recognized by others). Professional strategies and methods for their implementation are chosen. This stage is characterized by a deepening and continuity of the individual's connections with the professional environment.

5. "Integration into the Professional Environment."

At this stage, the individual experiences satisfaction with their profession, contributes creatively to transforming the professional environment, and senses their professional significance. The need to transfer accumulated experience becomes more active, communication skills develop, and recognition within the professional community increases. A continuous lifelong learning process is considered fundamental to maintaining professional development and high levels of professional mastery[5].

Engagement with the professional environment reflects an individual's interaction with this environment at all stages of their personal development. The timing and age boundaries of engagement phases are specific to each individual and depend on their professional affiliation and the peculiarities of the subjects of labor. When engagement develops according to the scenario described above, it indicates a "healthy" interaction between the individual and their environment. However, disruptions ("malfunctions") can sometimes occur, leading to changes, weakening, or complete loss of engagement. The loss of engagement signals a breakdown in the interaction process between the professional activity subject and the professional environment. The emergence of a "malfunction" indicates the appearance of conflicts that halt the individual's further development.

Unsuccessful progression through engagement stages leads to specific consequences, including: "Malfunctions in the First Stage" which result in the inability to focus attention on a particular profession—referred to as "diffusion of attention." In such cases, the individual struggles with career choice: no professional community appears attractive, and engagement with the professional environment does not form. If this stage prolongs for several years, it may lead to a profound "personal crisis." "Loss of Direction in the Professional Community" occurs at subsequent stages if the individual fails to understand or accept the norms and rules of the professional environment or lacks confidence in their ability to develop core professional competencies.

They may approach their chosen profession with doubt. In this case, professional preparation does not form, despite significant time and effort invested in education.

“Maladaptation (Disadaptation),” mainly characteristic of the “joining the professional environment” stage, reflects a disturbed interaction process between the labor subject and the professional environment, resulting in negative changes in professional activity [8]. The individual begins to demonstrate activity in professional work; however, their actions are disorganized and fail to produce expected results. This process is accompanied by low self-esteem and distrust in their ability to develop specific professional competencies.

“Professional Burnout manifests at the stage of integration into the professional environment.” At this point, the individual has mastered the chosen profession, adapted to the professional environment, and successfully performed professional activities for a certain period. The process of professional burnout is characterized by the loss of personal meaning in the performed activity, a decrease in motivation to perform professional duties effectively and efficiently, feelings of fatigue, and emotional exhaustion. As a result, the individual becomes socially withdrawn from the professional community and reduces interactions with professional groups.

“Professional stagnation (professional freeze) may appear at a subsequent stage, characterized by stereotyped thinking, behavior, and activity.” Professional stagnation manifests as the loss of desire to develop professional skills, decreased professional activity, indifference toward professional growth and career advancement, and a negative attitude towards innovations. Isolation may intensify. The individual may feel misunderstood and unaccepted within the professional environment, showing little initiative and lacking motivation to creatively transform their professional context. Thus, engagement with the professional environment is a continuous, holistic, systematic, and structured process expressing the specialist’s interaction with their professional surroundings.

An engaged specialist approaches professional activities with interest, dedicates their effort, time, energy, and resources to effective performance, professional growth, and development, maintains connections with the professional community, and monitors changes and innovations in their field. Hence, professional environment engagement implies, on one hand, the continuous improvement and updating of competencies that enable effective professional performance; on the other hand, it requires proactivity, understanding of developmental directions, and conscious awareness of competencies that need to be formed in the near future.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This ensures that the specialist remains capable of meeting demands and staying competitive. Currently, there is an increasing need to establish close links between the professional environment and continuous professional education. Thus, in our scholarly article, we have examined the structural model of engagement with continuous education, outlined the components of engagement, and identified its various forms.

Based on the analysis of scientific works by a number of authors, the following socio-psychological characteristics of learners’ engagement in lifelong learning can be identified:

1. Learners’ engagement in lifelong learning is an independent socio-psychological phenomenon that arises as a result of the interaction between learners and their social environment (educational institutions, study groups, professional representatives, teachers, etc.). Engagement is formed in a social context, through communication with others (socialization, entry into educational and professional environments) and during the performance of learning activities.

2. Engagement reflects the internal source of activity. It is dynamic, does not develop uniformly, manifests individually in each learner, and has unique characteristics. The stability of engagement is one of its important features. A learner’s engagement in the educational process is a necessary condition for the effectiveness of their learning activity and creative activity, as well as an integral characteristic of professional development.

3. Engagement is a multifaceted construct that, on the one hand, reflects the level of physical, mental, and psychological effort and exertion expended in performing activities, and on the other hand, reflects emotional experiences, cognitive, motivational, and meaningful processes related to the activity. The structure of learners’ engagement in lifelong learning consists of five components: cognitive, emotional, behavioral, motivational, and value-based. Among these components, objective and subjective elements can be distinguished.

4. Learners’ engagement can be expressed both quantitatively and qualitatively. Quantitative expression is manifested through behavior, while qualitative expression is described through the other components. One of the important characteristics of engagement is its level.

5. Learners’ engagement may take various forms: active engagement, obligatory engagement, passive engagement, or complete disengagement. Thus, engagement in lifelong learning is a multifaceted structure and phenomenon that includes perceptions, attitudes, emotional experiences, motives, and meanings related to education itself—its content, form, quality, and effectiveness—as well as to one’s own professional path. Behavioral activity and the amount of physical and psychological energy invested in educational activities are

the external manifestations of engagement. Engagement is formed through social interaction processes; it arises in a specific social context, is closely connected with social and professional adaptation processes, and is considered a socio-psychological phenomenon.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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